

PITA CASE APPLICATION REPORT

REMOTE
PATIENT
MONITORING
SYSTEM
(PMS)

Executive summary

This report documents the application of a tree-based privacy threat modeling approach called PITA (Privacy Impact Tree Analysis) to the Patient Monitoring System (PMS).

Part I of the report provides a comprehensive description of the application case.

The application of the PITA approach is provided in Part II of this report and starts with the specification of a Data Flow Diagram (DFD). After that, the step-by-step application of the PITA framework is illustrated, leading to a number of knowledge structures: *Privacy impact trees*. Finally, a privacy footprint analysis is performed, aggregating the impact of the system as a whole.

Author: Dimitri Van Landuyt, Faculty of Economics and Business (FEB), KU Leuven, Belgium

Contact: dimitri.vanlanduyt@kuleuven.be

Part I

Case description

Context

The COVID-19 pandemic has created pressures on national health services that were previously unseen. One of the consequences is that incentives are increased for health care providers to seek for more efficient ways to treat and manage patients in an *extra-muros* context: outside of the hospital premises, while keeping beds maximally reserved for more acute treatments. The recent technological development of telemedicine services, paired with the ubiquity of sensing devices and the Internet-of-Things serves as an additional accelerator to this trend [cowie2021remote](#).

Cardiovascular diseases. Heart diseases or cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are a class of diseases that involve the heart or blood vessels (arteries and veins). While the term technically refers to any disease that affects the cardiovascular system, it is usually used to refer to those related to arteriosclerosis (arterial disease). This is a condition in which an artery wall thickens as the result of a build-up of fatty materials such as cholesterol. Arterial disease can lead to heart attacks and strokes. Other pathologies are hypertension, congestive heart failure, etc.

Population-based studies in the youth show that the precursors of heart diseases start in adolescence [proudfoot2019physical](#). CVDs are slow, in the sense that they develop over decades, but as they become more acute in older patients, CVD is often associated to a patients' age. Although some symptoms can be treated (for example, obstructed heart vessels can be bypassed), prevention is of utter importance (for example, change in diet). Smoking, hypertension, and other conditions can increase the risk by several times.

As the western world faces population aging, the impact of CVDs increases continually. Most countries face high and increasing rates of cardiovascular disease. In 2015, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) cost the EU economy over 210 billion, and of this total cost, 111bn Euro (53%) was spent on health care, 45bn Euro (21%) in informal care costs, 32bn Euro (15%) due to early mortality; and 23bn Euro (11%) due to absence from work or early retirement [cvd:statistics](#). The priority in CVD treatment is on:

1. Primary prevention and timely diagnosis of the disease, and to
2. Management of the disease, i.e. prediction and prevention of malignant events (e.g., heart failure) after diagnosis.

E-health and telemedicine. *Electronic health* has large potential for increasing the quality of care delivered to patients, while decreasing overall health care costs. It can therefore mainly contribute to the management of CVDs, less to the primary prevention and timely di-

agnosis. The term “e-health” is defined broadly, grouping all types of health care practice supported by electronic processes and communication. It ranges from medical knowledge management (medical journals, etc.) to software solutions for appointment scheduling and patient data management ¹.

Another instance of e-health is the centralization of patient data in an *electronic health record* (EHR) which enables different health care professionals to communicate patient data in a fast, efficient and reliable way. *Telemedicine* is another instance of e-health, which enables the remote treatment and monitoring of patients, for example at home. As opposed to treatment and monitoring at the hospital, telemedicine has the potential to drastically cut costs in hospitalization.

A patient monitoring service or system focuses not so much on active treatment, but on monitoring of the patient and the disease. It offers extensive and up-to-date information to the physician without being overly obtrusive in the patients’ day-to-day life. By continually monitoring the patient, the physician can predict and therefore prevent malignant events, for example by changing the diagnosis or adapting the treatment.

Positioning

In this application case, we assume the point of view of a startup software company that enters the market with a novel patient monitoring service (PMS) for the management of cardiovascular diseases (CVD). At this initial stage of the development, collaboration with a local hospital for pilot studies is already arranged. Although this service is being built with one specific hospital in mind, it would evidently be beneficial for our company if we can extend our offering to other hospitals as well.

The goal is to offer the PMS *as a service*: instead of developing, selling or licensing the software as-is, our company will provide and maintain a patient monitoring infrastructure which will interact with the hospital services. The system itself will be located and hosted outside of the hospital infrastructure, but it will be well-integrated in the existing hospital infrastructure or Hospital Information System (HIS), for example to access patient records, offer decision support functionalities to the cardiologist, for invoicing, etc. It will also synchronize data with Electronic Health Record (EHR) services.

Key innovations. Whereas existing systems and services are relatively rigid in how they support the different models (e.g., using static rule-based decision models), our service will flexibly apply innovative ML algorithms and classifiers ² (which are shown to out-

¹ eHealth - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, January 2021

² Rine Nakanishi, Piotr J Slomka, Richard Rios, Julian Betancur, Michael J Blaha, Khurram Nasir, Michael D Miedema, John A Rumberger, Heidi Gransar, Leslee J Shaw, et al. Machine learning adds to clinical and cag assessments in predicting 10-year chd and cvd deaths. *Cardiovascular Imaging*, 14(3):615–625, 2021; and Ankush D Jamthikar, Deep Gupta, Laura E Mantella, Luca Saba, John R Laird, Amer M Ishai, and Jeevit S Suri. Multiscale

perform traditional approaches³) to perform risk estimation on a frequent basis and monitor the evolution of CVD in specific patients.

Description of the problem domain

This section discusses the overall goals and requirements of the Patient Monitoring Service (PMS).

Overall System Goals

Figure 1: High-level timeline overview of the treatment of a CVD patient.

Figure 1 schematically outlines the typical evolution of CVD. The enrollment of a patient in the CVD monitoring scheme happens after primary diagnosis (T3 in Figure 1), and it ends when it is considered no longer necessary by the physician in the context of overall follow-up and CVD treatment. The main goal of the service is to offer a sound and patient-centric solution for continuous and remote monitoring, in support of timely decision making and accurate prediction of malignant events, without in turn being overly invasive in the patient's day-to-day life.

- **Continuous and remote monitoring.** Patient monitoring is a very powerful tool in treatment and management of long-term diseases such as CVD. Automated continuous patient monitoring can give physicians a detailed and up-to-date view on the evolution of the disease. Current technologies allow patients to be monitored 24/7 without the need for the patient to be confined in a hospital bed.
- **Timely decision making.** Continuous patient monitoring also aids health care professionals in their decision making, offering them an extensive and up-to-date view on the patient's status. This leads to improved diagnoses, while reducing the necessity of frequent in-person consultations.
- **Prediction of malignant events.** Furthermore, continuous monitoring of the patient's health status can predict malignant events

³ Ioannis A Kakadiaris, Michalis Vrigkas, Albert A Yen, Tatiana Kuznetsova, Matthew Budoff, and Morteza Naghavi. Machine learning outperforms acc/aha cvd risk calculator in mesa. *Journal of the American Heart Association*, 7(22):e009476, 2018

such as heart attacks. By automated prediction of such events, health care professionals can be notified in a timely fashion, and the occurrence of malignant events such as heart attacks can be prevented.

- **Invasiveness in the patient's day-to-day life.** To ensure acceptability of such a monitoring service, a patient should not be bound to one place for the monitoring to happen.

The remainder of this chapter zooms in on these four aspects of the patient monitoring service.

Continuous monitoring

To monitor CVD patients, many parameters are of relevance, such as the heart rate, weight, blood pressure, body temperature, etc. In the patient monitoring service, these measurements are provided by electronic sensors, but also directly by the user.

Wearable unit. The most important enabler for monitoring CVD patients is the *wearable unit*. This device bundles a number of sensors for CVD and is worn by the patient close to the heart, for example as a chest band. The wearable unit has a battery lifetime of at least 8 hours and is minimal in size in order to not hinder the patient. The wearable unit is a medical device capable of continually measuring the following medical parameters:

- the **heart rate** in beats per minute (bpm). Normal levels for a healthy person are between 60 bpm and 100 bpm. For correct interpretation, the heart rate values should be correlated with the activity level of the patient.
- a continuous **electrocardiograph** (ECG) which plots the electrical activity of the heart over time (see Figure 2). The fundamental parameters to evaluate are the **maximum ventricular rate** (maximal heart rate) in bpm, the presence of **ventricular arrhythmias** (abnormalities of the heart rate and rhythm) and the presence of ischemia signs (restriction in blood supply).
- the **respiratory rate** (based on sound). Normal levels for a healthy person are within 12 and 20 breaths per minute. This value also needs to be correlated to the activity level of the patient.
- the **blood oxygen level** in percentage. Normal levels for a healthy person are within 90% and 100%.
- the **blood pressure** (the pressure exerted by circulating blood upon the walls of blood vessels) in millimeters of mercury (mmHg).

Normal levels for a healthy person are within 85 mmHg and 140 mmHg systolic.

- the **activity level** using the accelerometer. The activity level is expressed as a single number.
- the **body temperature** in degrees Celsius. Normal levels for a healthy person are within 35 degrees and 37 degrees.

Figure 2: An ECG of a 26-year-old male.

Additional inputs. Next to the wearable unit, support for other measuring devices, sensors or services could be integrated in support of the patient monitoring service. For example, the patient's weight can be obtained (in kg.) with a smart scale. A GPS chip (e.g., in a smartphone) delivers info about the geographic location of the patient. In future implementations of the PMS, the service should also provide support for daily or weekly questionnaires to be filled in by the patient, which allows collecting different types of relevant information (e.g. on the patient's state of mind, activities, etc.). Many sensor-based lifestyle tracking applications already on the market collect relevant data which may be taken into account during the follow-up and treatment of CVD-related pathologies in a patient.

Patient gateway. Sensors will not communicate directly with the PMS back-end service, but the collected data will go through an intermediate device: the *patient gateway*. For practical reasons, the role of patient gateway will be filled in by the patient's smartphone and the gateway logic will be supported by a smartphone application specifically developed for the PMS.

Every sensor communicates directly with the gateway, which makes abstraction of specific communication technologies, protocols and channels, but is (most of the time) capable of connecting to the back-end services.

The data collected from the sensors and other inputs are aggregated by the gateway and transmitted to the patient monitoring service. The gateway never transmits raw data to the system, only processed values in packages. The exact contents of a data package and the transmission rate can be configured on the gateway. By de-

fault, the configuration is determined by the patient’s risk level (see Section I). For example, in case of low risk, only a single average blood pressure value for the monitoring period is required during the planned transmission. In case of high risk, it can be useful to acquire the maximum, minimum and average daily values. Table 1 provides an overview of the default configuration for high risk, which has the highest transmission rates. These default rates can be explicitly overwritten by a physician.

Parameter	Transmission rate	Derived measure
Heart rate	48/day	Avg, max, min, variance
ECG	24/day	Full ECG of 30 sec.
Respiratory rate	48/day	Avg, max, min
Oxygen level	24/day	Avg, max, min
Blood pressure	48/day	Avg, max, min
Activity level	4/day	Single value
Temperature	6/day	Avg

Table 1: Default configuration for high risk.

Next to periodically transmitting the measurements, the gateway also supports transmitting data on demand. The physician has the ability to request the measurements instantly, in which case the system pushes the request to the gateway. For example, to perform a remote consultation, the physician can pull the latest data in full detail.

Apart from synchronizing obtained data from the wearable unit to the PMS, the gateway application will provide a user interface to patients, allowing them to manage their devices (e.g., consult battery percentage), consult the obtained sensor data and risk values, follow-up on overall treatment, contact their GP or request support. It could even support a social network that allows CVD patients to share experiences.

Impact on day-to-day life. A consequence of the technological advances in low-power wearable sensors and mobile communication networks is that the patient is not bound to one place for the monitoring to happen. Monitoring is transparent and does not prohibit the patient from performing regular day-to-day activities. Obviously, in terms of invasiveness, specific attention is to be spent not only on physical interference but also on data privacy in general (cf. Section I).

Risk estimation and notifications

The system uses the monitoring data sent by the gateway to continuously make estimates of the patient’s current CVD health status and

the evolution therein. The underlying goal is to predict upcoming malignant events (such as a heart attacks) and keep the appropriate parties (general practitioner, cardiologist, etc.) up-to-date by sending notifications.

To achieve this, patients are divided into *risk levels* (low, medium, and high risk). The physician determines the initial risk level of a patient depending on the primary diagnosis.

After that, the system monitors the patient and continually estimates whether or not a patient’s risk level should change, using *clinical risk models*. These models combine different technologies such as data mining, machine learning, probability models (e.g., Bayesian networks) and ontologies to model the data and derive a risk estimate combining all given inputs. The inputs for the clinical risk models are:

1. the new data sent by the gateway,
2. the historical data in the system,
3. the pathologies of the patient (as determined by the physician), and
4. the current risk level.

Optionally, artifacts related to previous classifications are also used (e.g., specifically trained classifiers for one patient).

To clarify how this works, we provide the example of a very simple clinical risk model. This model estimates a patient’s risk using *thresholds* for each medical parameter, determined on a per-patient basis. These thresholds determine whether the monitored values are to be considered normal, worrisome or dangerous. Default values for each of these thresholds depend on the risk level of the patient, but the physician is able to override each of the threshold values. Table 2 shows the default threshold values for the systolic blood pressure parameter.

Risk level	Normal	Worrisome	Dangerous
Low	105–120	90–105, 120–150	80–90, 150–190
Medium	95–135	90–95, 135–160	80–90, 160–190
High	90–150	85–90, 150–170	80–85, 170–190

A different example is HeartScore heartscore which provides an interactive tool targeted at the general population and not at known high-risk CVD patients. It is not suitable for event detection, but it can be support decision-making and is definitely useful for patients as it shows their overall progress, and so integration of HeartScore-like calculations is definitely useful.

Table 2: Default thresholds for systolic blood pressure (mmHg).

Notice the wider ranges for patients with higher risk-levels. Because of their cardiovascular conditions, their normal values will be, for example, more elevated, than the normal values of low-risk patients.

It is generally accepted that no single clinical model is suited for all different CVD pathologies, and thus the system will need to support different clinical models. In addition, a single patient's CVD monitoring schedule is typically supported by multiple clinical models that employ different types of algorithms or are aimed at assessing different aspects. The overall outcome of a risk estimation for a single patient is then based on the combination of the outcomes of the individual clinical models selected for that patient. Some clinical model will be versatile or generic (and thus be deployed and configured system-wide), while others may be very specific to certain CVD pathologies, or even need to be configured on a per-patient basis. In any case, all risk calculations are executed by PMS.

The threshold-based risk model described above is obviously a highly simplistic example, and as discussed earlier, one of the innovative features of the new patient monitoring service is that it will rely on clinical risk models that incorporate more advanced Machine Learning classifiers. These are provided by a third party, an external research organization which specialized in CVD prediction and releases trained classifiers. This third party will provide trained models for specific pathologies and different risk levels, which can be used in the continuous monitoring of patients. These models can be updated over time. To be able to run these models, the PMS will use a machine learning framework.

The main goal of the patient monitoring service is to aid and support medical decision making, *not* to make actual medical decisions. Only the physician is granted authority to effectively change the risk level of the patient in the system.

If the system estimates that a patient's risk level should or may change (typically based on a number of different risk estimations and risk models), the physician is notified in order to assess the estimation and approve, revise or decline it.

In general, there are three notification levels: green, yellow, and red. These levels indicate the degree of urgency or priority with which the notification should be dealt with. A red notification is sent when the patient's status changes significantly and requires immediate and urgent attention. A yellow notification is sent when the patient's status changes non-critically but remains potentially dangerous. A green notification is sent when the patient's status reverts to a lower risk level. Of course, the exact content of the notification depends on the precise event.

Physician decision support

The medical models used for the estimation of patient risk levels are also used to aid physicians in their decision making, for example on a consultation. When a physician checks on the status of a patient, the most important and relevant information is shown in a structured and efficient way. For this, the system has to be able to evaluate the patient's status. Through the implementation of standard clinical models and by applying medical guidelines, routine clinical consultations are made more consistent and informative. For example, the system knows that the physician was recently notified of a malignant event with the patient. Now, the system shows the current risk estimate of the patient, together with all the information relevant to the event (for example, a graph of the blood pressure or an ECG). Of course, physicians are still able to request any additional information they want.

Patient support

Similarly to physicians, patients can also make use of the medical models. When patients want to check their own status, they also expect to see the most important and relevant information in a structured and efficient way. Of course, there is an important difference in the way this data is presented to these actors: in case of the patient, this data must not be too technical or clinical. The system offers patients a customized view on his data, for example a simple graph indicating the percentage improvement since last week.

Medical emergencies

As an extension to the green, yellow and red notifications, the system can also send *emergency notifications*. An emergency notification is sent to the Hospital Emergency services (cf. Section I) in case of a life-threatening event such as a heart attack. Emergency notifications are sent in case of *ongoing* emergencies, while other notifications are sent when malignant events are *predicted* or anticipated.

Regular notifications are sent by the system after analyzing new data using medical risk models. For emergencies, this system is too slow since the fastest transmission rate is 48 times per day. Therefore, the gateway is extended with a general-purpose, lightweight, medical emergency model, which is also threshold-based (as the one presented in Section I). Similar to the other risk models, default threshold values depend on the patient's risk level but can be explicitly overwritten by a physician.

The gateway uses this model to interpret the measurements itself

and alerts the system of a possible emergency, along with the necessary data. The system re-checks the data for an emergency using more extensive models and sends out an emergency notification if needed. Note however, that we are not building a live-saving device: handling emergencies is not a primary goal of the system, and the timely delivery of an emergency notification should not be guaranteed in every case.

Main stakeholders

Patients. The system applies to patients who have already been diagnosed with CVD and now need to be monitored for treating or controlling their disease (which does not hold for every CVD patient). They want the system to help them in the treatment and management of the disease and would like this to happen in the most comfortable way.

Physicians. The system will be used by different types of physicians. In practice, cardiovascular disease is treated by specialists such as cardiologists, thoracic surgeons, vascular surgeons, neurologists, and radiologists, depending on the organ system that is being treated. Another important stakeholder in this context is also the patient's general practitioner (GP) who keeps a holistic overview of overall patient health.

The system should support these physicians in their job, primarily by aiding their decision making. Physicians want the information they need in a structured and efficient way, for example by being notified of important updates of a patient's status or a clean graph of the patient's evolution. Also note that we are building a system for use by a hospital, but not every physician needs to be in that same location. A GP typically has their own independent practice, and often specialists also hold practice outside of hospital premises.

Nurses. Nurses are responsible for the more practical part of the patient's treatment. In general, nurses at the hospital do not take part directly in the system. However, a specialized team is responsible for the setup and configuration of the sensors after a patient has been diagnosed and recommended to use the system.

Emergency call center. The emergency call center in the hospital receives all emergency calls and responds appropriately, for example by dispatching an ambulance to the scene. They also receive emergency notifications from the monitoring service. With an emergency, they want to receive as much information as possible to correctly assess the situation and the urgency to determine the most appropriate response. Therefore, they also want to access the detailed monitoring information. Moreover, an emergency notification also needs to be

entered in the system so other appropriate parties (the specialist, the GP etc.) can be notified to be kept up-to-date.

Telemedicine operators. The telemedicine operators deal with issues and provide technical and setup support, ranging from patients who notice that their wearable unit is malfunctioning, to a hospital administrator who notices that data updates are not working correctly.

The telemedicine operators also follow up the overall management of the system. They integrate risk models and deal with updates and upgrades of the functionality, provisioning system resources, etc. They are notified by the system when a patient's sensor has not sent in data for a long time or the data seems incorrect (e.g., impossible outliers). They handle notifications where further human assessment is needed to determine further actions.

The hospital. As mentioned in Section I, our company's first client is a specific hospital. More specifically, we—as a telemedicine company—have been contracted for a pilot project, involving only a limited number of CVD patients. If successful, the hospital will deploy and apply this monitoring service to a larger patient base in the future.

The hospital's main stake is that the patient monitoring service will aid them in raising the quality of CVD treatment, thereby increasing the efficiency and effectiveness of CVD treatment. Furthermore, by introducing CVD patient monitoring from home, CVD patients are kept out of the hospital and this frees up space and resources allocated previously for on premise patient monitoring.

Electronic health record service. The Electronic Health Record (EHR) service collects patients' health records from diverse health organizations and provides different physicians with an efficient means to consult patient data while also providing patients with access to their own records. This service can be performed by an individual hospital itself or by a specialized third party, for example one service used by all hospitals and physicians in a geographic region. The data collected by the patient monitoring service will eventually be integrated into the patient's EHR and kept up to date via the HIS.

Legal departments. Both the legal department of our company as well as that of the hospital need the system to comply to health care regulations. More information about the precise health care regulations can be found in Section I. It is important the system is not only compliant to these regulations by design but is provably compliant throughout its operation.

Hospital financial department. The hospital financial department is responsible for invoicing their customers, the patients. It is imper-

ative that the systems provide clear usage and billing reports so that this is done correctly.

Telecom operators. Telecom operators provide means for the sensors and the gateways to communicate with the system. A service level agreement (SLA) between our company and the telecom operators determines the capabilities of these communication channels.

ML model provider. This stakeholder represents a clinical research institute that trains and prepares specific Machine Learning models tailored to specific pathologies under the broader CVD umbrella. This institute allows downloading these models and classifiers, which can in turn be executed using a ML framework. This third party also prepares regular updates and improvements to these models.

Main building blocks and constraints

Next to the general problem domain description, there are a number of specific constraints highly relevant to the patient monitoring service.

Hospital Information System (HIS)

As mentioned in Section I, the patient monitoring service will be deployed and maintained as a standalone platform by our company. Nonetheless, it should integrate tightly with the existing Hospital Information System (HIS) currently in use at the hospital. A relevant resource in this specific respect is the HL7 FHIR (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) standard ⁴ which is widely adopted in the e-health domain. The desired integration covers a number of dimensions:

Patient data. Evidently, the hospital retains full control of patient records and patient data, and the patient monitoring service (PMS) will not change this. This implies that the measurements gathered by the PMS must be integrated in the patient record storage of the hospital itself. However, keep in mind that some of the measured data (cf. Section I) is very fine-grained and updated frequently.

Physician workstation. As part of the existing HIS, the physician (e.g., a cardiologist) already has a means to connect to the hospital, either through their personal workstation or remotely (if they have their own practice), to consult patient records, extend notes of patient consultations, etc. As the patient monitoring service offers the physician with a number of new functionalities related to decision support, remote configuration of the sensors, daily patient follow-up and receiving notifications, these must be integrated in the physician's workstation.

⁴ The standard specifications can be found at <https://hl7.org/fhir/>.

Patient registration. When a patient is first introduced to the monitoring service, they receive a wearable unit containing a set of sensors. First, these must be paired or linked to the specific patient. Secondly, they must be initialized and calibrated according to the patient's context, and this setup must be tested before sending the patient home. This process of patient registration happens at the hospital (e.g., after a check-up), and is conducted by a trained nurse.

Emergency situation. When the automated decision support identifies an emergency situation (cf. Section I), it must be able to trigger an emergency procedure by contacting the emergency services already offered by the hospital (e.g., 112) and possibly also the other stakeholders involved in the patient's treatment, such as his physician and GP.

Accounting. Finally, for purposes of accounting, the hospital must be kept aware on a day-to-day basis of the costs incurred during operation of the patient monitoring service. Typical costs include the maintenance of the platform (e.g., repairing sensors), computational cost (e.g., to perform risk assessment), storage costs, bandwidth costs, and operation costs of the call-center.

Financial constraints

Evidently, setting up and maintaining a pilot project such as the one described in this assignment is a costly operation. For this project, our company has negotiated a million-euro contract with one specific hospital. Since the pilot project involves monitoring of actual CVD patients, a Service-Level Agreement (SLA) has been enclosed as part of this contract. This agreement stipulates certain quality requirements (in terms of performance and availability). For example, there should be an upper limit in the time it takes for an emergency notification to reach its destination.

Also, our company has to negotiate a number of service-level agreements with several of third parties: the telecom operator to ensure the desired degree of patient connectivity, the hardware manufacturer for acquisition, maintenance, upgrade and repair, etc.

Legal constraints

Because the data handled in the system is medical data, the system has to comply to several laws. In the EU, medical information is regarded as personal information and falls under the General Data Protection Regulation ⁵ (GDPR). Without going into too much detail, the main guiding principles are:

- Health information cannot be collected and used without explicit

⁵ European Union. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 59(L 119):1–88, May 2016

patient consent, and in this case only for purposes of continuous CVD treatment, unless processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the patient (e.g., emergencies), payment or administration of the service.

- Disclosure of identity information should be minimized: if the data can be anonymized or de-identified, it should be (e.g., when opening up the data for research purposes).
- Patient should be able to locate and view all of their health information. They should also be able to delete and modify all personal administrative information (right to rectification, right to removal, etc.).
- Health data should be stored for a number of years, depending on the country (30 years in Belgium, 6 years in the US).
- Accountability: anytime the patient's data is disclosed to a third party, this event should be monitored and logged.

The system should apply to at least all rules stated above.

Security

Considering the nature of the patient monitoring service (patient health information is considered sensitive information) and the legal implications listed above, it is evident that security is key concern in the system. In this assignment we limit the scope to *user authentication* and *user action logging*.

User authentication. Authentication is the process of ensuring the identity of the different actors. It should not be possible for a user to act as another user (spoofing) and users should not be able to access the system unauthorized. It is clear that the patient monitoring service has a large variety of types of users, and it is realistic that the concrete realization of authentication will differ highly between these users: for example, physicians may use a badge to authenticate themselves, whereas patients may be authenticated implicitly, because they are using a wearable unit that is linked to his identity.

User action logging. Logging is the process of storing information about every action performed by the actors and the system itself. It enables the checking of system compliance to business or security policies, or in case of security-related incidents, trace the incident to a user. A log contains information such as the identity of the actor, the action, the object on which the action is performed, a timestamp etc. Note that user action logging depends on correct user authentication.

Part II

PITA application

PMS Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

The PMS equips CVD patients with wearable sensing devices that keep track of a variety of medical parameters. Via an app installed on the patient's smartphone (the gateway), data is buffered and synchronized with the back-end of the PMS. Local medical risk assessment is performed continuously and if required, medical emergencies are notified. In the back-end, more complex, ML-based models are employed to evaluate the patient's risk level and health evolution. If needed, the gateway is reconfigured remotely, and GP or emergency services are notified.

Figure 3: HomeSys Data flow diagram (DFD).

The Data Flow Diagram (DFD) shown in Figure 3 presents the overall architectural overview of the PMS system. This is the basis for the evaluation of privacy threats.

We follow the steps of the PITA approach.

1. Elicitation phase.

1.1. Identify data subject types

The following data subjects may be involved in a PMS instance:

- **Patient:** The PMS continuously collects and records sensitive medical parameters of Patients, processes and propagates them and makes them available to a number of relevant stakeholders.
- **GP:** The GP interacts with the PMS system as part of their normal remote follow-up of patients. This is encoded in specific business processes.
- **Emergency service operator:** The emergency service provider received signals when a possible medical emergency is detected. In this case, additional identifying information (patient ID, sensor data, location information, etc) are shared.
- **ML Model Developer:** The ML Model developer uploads new and updates models that are used for risk evaluation. There is fine-grained differentiation as different types of ML Models are provided for different conditions and types of CVD ailment.

1.2. Instantiate privacy impact tree roots

We identify and list the following possible negative privacy outcomes (privacy impact instances) of the PMS. The Privacy Impact types that

are instantiated by these examples have been underlined.

- **T1.** Detectable exposure of patient status to bystanders (Exposure): the system in its embedding in the patient's environment may allow other persons to recognize or identify a specific patient as a CVD patient.
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **High**, to allow CVD patients to maximally function in their day-to-day actions, they would not like to be visibly exposed as CVD patients.
- **T2.** Exposure of patients to medical personnel (Exposure): the medical parameters may allow persons with access to this raw data (e.g, GP, HIS) to infer specific unrelated, properties of the patients, e.g. types of activities, recurrent habits, ...
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **High**, the data should be minimized to what is strictly needed for CVD monitoring, and the processing purely in function of that.
- **T3.** Patient is uninformed about risk level changes (Lack of explanation), and that perhaps a risk level increase leads to more fine-grained and frequent data collection The system may decide to change, this may cause undue stress in Patients when not properly explained and motivated.
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Medium**, the recipient may not even be aware of the risk level or of the exact meaning of these.
- **T4.** PMS overshares the consolidated medical data sets (Propagation) e.g. by selling to the ML Providers for purposes of model optimization and training
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **High** , the data has been obtained for a specific purpose (CVD monitoring of specific patients), but this legal basis may be stretched as such for other purposes such as the one discussed above.
- **T5.** PMS data sharing with HIS is too detailed (Propagation) e.g. location traces, other meta-data.
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Medium**, HIS already obtains fine grained data CVD-related data. PMS adds more recurrence of already made medical observations.
- **T6.** Sensor malfunction leads to improper treatment of patients (Inaccuracy). When sensor data is incorrect, it may lead to wrong impactful medical decisions, and thus incur health risks.
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **High**

- **T7.** The PMS remote monitoring capabilities are used for patient surveillance (Surveillance)
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Medium**
- **T8.** The PMS patient data leads to a loss of plausible deniability (Loss of deniability) e.g. having performed an action, having been at a location
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Medium**
- **T9.** Identifying the patient from patient data (loss of anonymity), e.g. a patient might have unique biometric properties which may be visible in the collected patient data.
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Low**, as this not an expectation when using a system such as the PMS. Patient data is supposed the be identified.
- **T10.** Advanced analytics of patient data for other purposes beyond CVD monitoring (Analysis)
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Medium**, there is no incentive for PMS
- **T11.** Inference of recurring patterns and habits in GP's data (Inference)
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Medium**, as the exposure to PMS is only sporadic and recurrent.
- **T12.** GP interaction data used for comparing and ranking different GPs (Comparative profiling)
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Low**, this does not really have any personal implications.
- **T13.** GP underestimates impact of risk level change decisions (Lack of feedback), e.g. in terms of mental or privacy cost) on the Patient
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Low**, as this is not a pure privacy issue.
- **T14.** Active inference attack on patient data in the training sets of the ML models (membership inference), (Inference)
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **Low**, these patients are not expected to be directly involved in the PMS or known
- **T15.** Lack of proper access control in the HIS leads to publication or leak of patient data (Publication)
 - *Extent of impact-score:* **High**

- **T16.** PMS makes impactful decisions without human intervention or oversight (Lack of Oversight); autonomous decision making.
 - *Extent of impact-score: **Medium***, increased as monitoring rate does not have any other effect.
- **T17.** Discrimination against CVD patients based on exposure (Discrimination)
 - *Extent of impact-score: **High***,

1.3. Expand privacy impact trees

We expand the privacy impact cases with a High Extent-score, and propagate this Extent downwards to the leaf nodes.

T1: Detectable exposure of patient status to bystanders. This tree explores the possibility of disclosure or detection of the involvement of a person in the CVD monitoring scheme. Simply leaking the involvement of a person would potentially lead to negative consequences such as discrimination (cf. T17). Figure 4 presents the corresponding tree.

Among a number of paths, it also takes into account the possibility of detection via network traffic analysis (e.g. over a guest wifi network, or by an ISP).

T2: Exposure of patients to medical personnel. This tree takes into account the possibility of overdisclosing patient information through the shared medical parameters to the medical personnel that is interacting with this data (HIS and GP sides). It considers whether these stakeholders get access to raw and unprocessed data rather than compiled or aggregated representations. The resulting tree is presented in Figure 5.

T4: PMS overshares the consolidated medical data sets. This privacy impact tree considers the possibility of collected medical

Figure 4: T1. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible detection of CVD health patients. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

Figure 5: T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible overexposure of patients to the medical personnel. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

data sets being repurposed or sold, for secondary usages. The tree is presented in Figure 6.

Figure 6: T4. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible repurposing or oversharing of medical data. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

T6: Sensor malfunction leads to improper treatment of patients. This tree evaluates the possibility of inaccurate medical data and its medical and privacy implications. It explores presence of different techniques to ensure accuracy (detect or prevent inaccuracy). The tree is presented in Figure 7.

T15: Lack of proper access control in the HIS leads to publication or leak of patient data. We evaluate possible privacy impacts that occur when the HIS itself is not properly protecting the synchronized details patient data in its medical records. The tree is depicted in Figure 8.

T17: Discrimination against CVD patients based on exposure . Finally, we expand a privacy impact tree that investigates the possibility of negative discrimination outcomes being based on the exposure of CVD patient statuses, and the extent to which this practice might be exacerbated thanks to the PMS. The tree is depicted in Figure 9.

Figure 7: T4. Privacy impact tree that explores possible outcomes where inaccurate data have bigger implications. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

Figure 8: T15. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the HIS is not properly protecting the synchronized data, leading to broader leakage or publication. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

Figure 9: T17. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the PMS contributes to discriminatory outcomes against CVD patients. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually.

1.4. Evaluate and propagate Exposure-scores.

In the Privacy Impact Tree Figures presented in the previous section, the Exposure-scores of the leafs has already been indicated. We have attached a Exposure-score to each tree leaf, and then used the mechanism of upwards propagation toward the tree root. This completes the specification and prioritization of the privacy impact trees.

In each of the examples, we have annotated the propagated (deduced) value in *italics*.

The results can be seen in Figures 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15.

Figure 10: T1. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible detection of CVD health patients, after propagating Exposure-scores.

Figure 11: T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible overexposure of patients to the medical personnel, after propagating Exposure-scores.

2. Mitigation phase.

2.1. Select a leaf node

In the mitigation phase, we systematically focus on the privacy impact trees with the highest Extent and Exposure scores. For PMS,

Figure 12: T4. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible repurposing or oversharing of medical data, after propagating Exposure-scores.

Figure 13: T6. Privacy impact tree that explores possible outcomes where inaccurate data have bigger implications, after propagating Exposure-scores.

Figure 14: T15. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the HIS is not properly protecting the synchronized data, leading to broader leakage or publication, after propagating Exposure-scores.

Figure 15: T17. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the PMS contributes to discriminatory outcomes against CVD patients, after propagating Exposure-scores.

based on the results presented above, these are the following three trees:

- **T2: Exposure of patients to medical personnel.** Here, we address the two leaves *“In explicit meta-data (e.g. location, ip)”* and *“Inference at the basis of PMS data (e.g. activity type)”*.
- **T4: PMS overshares the consolidated medical data sets.** Here, we would select the leaf *“Improper access control in HIS”*
- **T15: Lack of proper access control in the HIS leads to publication or leak of patient data.** Here, we select the right hand leaf: *“Data accessible and readable for example in system logs or network traffic inspection”*.

2.2. Mitigation

We introduce a number of mitigations in the respective privacy impact trees.

Figure 16 shows the result for the T2 privacy impact tree. As shown, we introduce two complementary privacy mitigations in the selected leaf nodes, one to remove unnecessary metadata that may be the basis for overexposure, and another to transform the data sets for increasing privacy without loss of utility.

In T4, the offending leaf is outside of the system’s control. Here, there is no possible technical mitigation, as we would rely entirely on trust to the third party (HIS) to implement proper access management.

Finally, in T15, we decide to encrypt traffic in motion and obfuscate data included in system logs to mitigate the identified privacy

Figure 16: T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible overexposure of patients to the medical personnel, after introducing privacy mitigations.

risks. The resulting tree is shown in Figure 17.

Figure 17: T15. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the HIS is not properly protecting the synchronized data, leading to broader leakage or publication, after introducing privacy mitigations.

Calculating the privacy footprint score of PMS

We now illustrate how these outcomes can be aggregated in an expression of the overall PMS *privacy footprint*.

For demonstration purposes, this is done at the basis of the High-impact trees detailed above.

We annotate for each tree node whether it is affected by the system and its design choices.

Table 3 summarizes the trees and compares the a-priori and a-posteriori risks. In the final row, it summarizes and aggregates these results into an expression of the overall privacy footprint of PMS.

The number printed between brackets counts the number of branches contributing to this aggregated Exposure score.

Figure 18: T1. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible detection of CVD health patients. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated

Figure 19: T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible overexposure of patients to the medical personnel. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 20: T4. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible repurposing or oversharing of medical data. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 21: T6. Privacy impact tree that explores possible outcomes where inaccurate data have bigger implications. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 22: T15. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the HIS is not properly protecting the synchronized data, leading to broader leakage or publication. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Figure 23: T17. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the PMS contributes to discriminatory outcomes against CVD patients. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated.

Through comparing the a-priori situation to the a-posteriori situation, we can reason about the overall privacy footprint of the PMS system.

Similarly, we show the a-posteriori situation that takes into account the integrated mitigations.

Privacy impact tree	<u>Extent</u>	A-priori	<u>Exposure</u> A- posteriori- no mitigations	A posteriori- mitigations
T1: Detectable exposure of patient status to bystanders (Figure 18)	H	M (2)	M (3)	M(3)
T2: Exposure of patients to medical personnel. (Figure 19)	H	o	H (2)	L(2)
T4: PMS overshares the consolidated medical data sets.. (Figure 20)	H	o	H (1)	H(1)
T6: Sensor malfunction leads to improper treatment of patients (Figure 21)	H	o	L (1)	L (1)
T15: Lack of proper access control in the HIS leads to publication or leak of patient data (Figure 22)	H	M (2)	H	M (3)
T17: Discrimination against CVD patients based on exposure. (Figure 23)	H	M	M	M
Privacy footprint $f(PMS)$	H	o (3) M (5)	L (1) M (3) H (4)	L (3) M (7) H (1)

Table 3: List of the expanded impact trees, summarizing Extent-score and a-priori and the a-posteriori Exposure-scores, both without taking into account the privacy mitigations and with. The bottom row aggregates the overall privacy footprint.

Contents

I Case description 3

II PITA application 19

Bibliography 39

List of Figures

- 1 High-level timeline overview of the treatment of a CVD patient. 7
- 2 An ECG of a 26-year-old male. 9
- 3 HomeSys Data flow diagram (DFD). 21
- 4 T1. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible detection of CVD health patients. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually. 24
- 5 T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible overexposure of patients to the medical personnel. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually. 25
- 6 T4. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible repurposing or over-sharing of medical data. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually. 25
- 7 T4. Privacy impact tree that explores possible outcomes where inaccurate data have bigger implications. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually. 26
- 8 T15. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the HIS is not properly protecting the synchronized data, leading to broader leakage or publication. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually. 26
- 9 T17. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the PMS contributes to discriminatory outcomes against CVD patients. Scores printed in bold have been determined manually. 26
- 10 T1. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible detection of CVD health patients, after propagating Exposure-scores. 27
- 11 T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible overexposure of patients to the medical personnel, after propagating Exposure-scores. 27
- 12 T4. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible repurposing or over-sharing of medical data, after propagating Exposure-scores. 28
- 13 T6. Privacy impact tree that explores possible outcomes where inaccurate data have bigger implications. after propagating Exposure-scores. 28
- 14 T15. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the HIS is not properly protecting the synchronized data, leading to broader leakage or publication, after propagating Exposure-scores. 28

- 15 T17. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the PMS contributes to discriminatory outcomes against CVD patients, after propagating Exposure-scores. 29
- 16 T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible overexposure of patients to the medical personnel, after introducing privacy mitigations. 30
- 17 T15. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the HIS is not properly protecting the synchronized data, leading to broader leakage or publication, after introducing privacy mitigations. 30
- 18 T1. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible detection of CVD health patients. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated 31
- 19 T2. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible overexposure of patients to the medical personnel. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated. 31
- 20 T4. Privacy impact tree that explores the possible repurposing or over-sharing of medical data. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated. 31
- 21 T6. Privacy impact tree that explores possible outcomes where inaccurate data have bigger implications. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated. 32
- 22 T15. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the HIS is not properly protecting the synchronized data, leading to broader leakage or publication. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated. 32
- 23 T17. Privacy impact tree that explores possible cases where the PMS contributes to discriminatory outcomes against CVD patients. Distinction between a priori and a posteriori impacts has been annotated. 32

Bibliography

- [1] eHealth - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, January 2021.
- [2] European Union. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 59(L 119):1–88, May 2016.
- [3] Ankush D Jamthikar, Deep Gupta, Laura E Mantella, Luca Saba, John R Laird, Amer M Johri, and Jasjit S Suri. Multiclass machine learning vs. conventional calculators for stroke/cvd risk assessment using carotid plaque predictors with coronary angiography scores as gold standard: a 500 participants study. *The International Journal of Cardiovascular Imaging*, 37(4):1171–1187, 2021.
- [4] Ioannis A Kakadiaris, Michalis Vrigkas, Albert A Yen, Tatiana Kuznetsova, Matthew Budoff, and Morteza Naghavi. Machine learning outperforms acc/aha cvd risk calculator in mesa. *Journal of the American Heart Association*, 7(22):e009476, 2018.
- [5] Rine Nakanishi, Piotr J Slomka, Richard Rios, Julian Betancur, Michael J Blaha, Khurram Nasir, Michael D Miedema, John A Rumberger, Heidi Gransar, Leslee J Shaw, et al. Machine learning adds to clinical and cac assessments in predicting 10-year chd and cvd deaths. *Cardiovascular Imaging*, 14(3):615–625, 2021.